

+
Our
Future
Health

Our Future Health

A world-leading platform for discovery,
aetiological and translational research

Dr Ryan Arathimos
Senior Statistical Geneticist

- Programme overview
- Available data
- Access process
- Challenges and learnings

+ Our Future Health

Our Future Health is a not-for-profit organisation which aims to recruit **5 million UK adults** to a prospective cohort that will **catalyse aetiological and translational research for both common and rare diseases.**

The recency, relevancy and size of the data are providing for **population health insights** and **evidence-based health policy.**

Translational research will be facilitated by **access to stored biosamples** and **selective invitation of participants into your trials and studies.**

Funders

Affiliate Charities

+
Our
Future
Health

Age
18+

UK
resident

Our Volunteers

Reflective of the population
across England, Wales, Scotland,
and Northern Ireland by

Age

Sex

Ethnicity

Deprivation

+ Participant Journey

Awareness/Engagement

In partnership with **NHS**

Address
Address
Address

2,409,439 people are already taking part in the UK's largest health research programme.
(As of 29 April 2025)

Dear [First name],

An opportunity to take part in research and learn new information about your blood pressure and future risk of disease.

You are invited to take part in Our Future Health, the UK's largest ever health research programme. If you take part, you will have the chance to find out more about your health now, and your risk of developing some diseases in the future.

Today, too many people spend many years of their life in poor health. Our Future Health aims to help prevent, detect and treat diseases earlier. Diseases like dementia, cancer, diabetes, heart disease and stroke.

Our Future Health needs up to 5 million people. Everyone aged 18 and over living in the UK is eligible to take part.

Taking part includes answering some online questions about yourself, providing a blood sample, and having your blood pressure measured at a local clinic.

In the future Our Future Health plans to offer you the chance to learn about your risk of developing some diseases such as diabetes and heart disease. This would be calculated using the information you provide and an analysis of the DNA in your blood sample.

Scan this QR code for more info and to sign up
Or visit ourfuturehealth.org.uk/join/0449

£10 voucher
Sign up using the QR code or website link above and you will be eligible for a £10 voucher to recognise the time and effort of volunteering. You can find more information on the back of this letter.

You can also share this invitation with other members of your household.
If you have any questions, please call 0808 501 5634 or email support@ourfuturehealth.org.uk

Yours sincerely,
Rajesh Ab
Rajesh Ab OBE MD FRCP(UK)
Chief Medical Officer, Our Future Health
NHS Consultant in Acute Medicine

Professor Sir John Bell
Professor Sir John Bell CBE, FRS
Chairman, Our Future Health

Our Future Health is a company with the Charity Commission number SC050817. Registered. A charity registered under the Companies Act 2006.

Let's prevent disease together

Our Future Health is the UK's largest ever health research programme.

At Our Future Health, our goal is to help future generations live in good health for longer.

We are aiming to collect information and samples from up to 5 million adults to build the most detailed picture ever of the UK's health.

Researchers will be able to apply to use this information to make new discoveries about health and disease.

Discoveries made through Our Future Health could lead to new ways to predict, prevent and detect diseases like dementia, cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and stroke.

We're inviting people aged over 18 from all backgrounds across the UK. Because to help all kinds of people, we need every kind of person.

[Start now](#)

Register

Enter your details to register

Registration Participant information Consent form Questionnaire

About you

First name

Last name

Date of birth
For example, 31 3 1980
Day Month Year

Information

You'll need to complete the following steps online:

1. Register by creating an account
2. Read about the programme (Participant information)
3. Consent to take part
4. Complete a questionnaire about you and your health (5 sections)

After joining, you'll be sent a kit to provide a sample of your saliva, which you'll need to send back to us.

Consent

Consent Form

Chief Investigator: Dr Andrew Roddam of Our Future Health

If you wish to take part in the Our Future Health research programme, please complete the following form to show you understand and agree to what it involves. You need to tick all boxes from 1 to 11 to be eligible to take part.

1. I have read and understood the Our Future Health participant information sheet dated 5 March 2021 (version 1.1). I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and these have been answered fully.
2. I understand that taking part in Our Future Health is my choice.
3. I understand that Our Future Health will access, store and link to health-related records about me held by NHS Digital and other UK third parties. I understand that Our Future Health can collect and use this information for research analysis at any point during my lifetime and beyond.
4. I understand that samples of blood and/or saliva that I give to Our Future Health will be stored and analysed in future health-related research. I understand that my de-personalised samples and data could be sent to approved processors outside the UK for analysis.
5. I understand that DNA will be extracted from my blood and/or saliva samples. I understand that my DNA will be analysed for health-related research using a technology called SNP array, and that other technologies might also be used, such as genome sequencing.
6. I understand that Our Future Health might contact me again in the future, including to:
 - send me news and updates about the research programme
 - ask me about my experiences of taking part
 - ask me to complete another questionnaire
 - ask my permission to collect health relevant information about me from other sources
 - invite me to attend an appointment to give a (further) blood sample
 - invite me to attend an appointment for other assessments, such as imaging
 - ask if I would like to receive personal information arising from my samples or data
 - invite me to take part in other research studies.
7. I understand that researchers approved to access the information collected by Our Future Health could be from

Physical measurements

Blood sample

Account | Sign out

Dashboard Frequently Asked Questions Help and support

1. About you and your household 2. Work and education 3. Your lifestyle 4. Family health history 5. Your health history

Questionnaire help and guidance

1. About you and your household
To which gender identify do you most identify?

[Previous question](#) [Save and continue](#)

Questionnaire

+ What our participants donate to Our Future Health

Complete a baseline questionnaire (demographics & household, work & education, lifestyle, family history, personal health history)

Physical measurements taken at clinic appointment (height, weight, waist circumference, blood pressure, heart rate)

A blood sample for genotyping and for long-term storage of plasma, buffy coat, and DNA

DNA is genotyped using a custom array that captures 700k up-to-date variants of interest for optimal research insights

Provide permission for data linkage to health-related datasets (e.g., primary care, secondary care, cancer, death)

Provide permission to be recontacted for further surveys/biospecimens/assessments and to be invited to additional studies/trials

+ Baseline health questionnaire

288 questions grouped into five sections.

- **About you and your household** – for example, age, sex, height, weight, ethnicity and living situation
- **Work and education** – for example, income, employment history and highest educational attainment
- **Lifestyle** – for example, socialising, screen use and alcohol intake
- **Family health history** – for example, siblings' and parents' health
- **Personal health history** – for example, health check-ups and screenings, diagnoses, medications and any current symptoms

68 core questions, 220 dynamic questions – shown based on previous responses

[Questionnaire and answers by section](#)

<https://ourfuturehealth.gitbook.io/our-future-health/data/questionnaire-data>

The Our Future Health custom genotype array types 700,000 variants for aetiologic and translational research

- GWAS backbone is **optimised for multi-ethnic imputation capability**.
- Design incorporates **up to date sets of disease- and phenotype-associated genetic variants** from the Genotype Assay Working Group including polygenic risk score (PRS), GWAS catalog, ACMG, and ClinVar sets.
- The array is also designed for **pharmacogenetic research and to accurately predict blood types** to further enhance healthcare insights.
- We have built an integrated genotyping workflow and have contracted with Genomics Ltd for imputation, genetic ancestry, and polygenic risk scores.

BIOMARKERS AND POTENTIAL UTILITY OF THE GENOTYPING DATA

Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS)

- Complex diseases are influenced by **multiple genetic and environmental factors**.
- Common complex diseases include cancer, cardiometabolic, neurological, autoimmune, and respiratory diseases with enormous health and economic impact.
- For participants with imputed data, Genomics Ltd generated polygenic risk scores for **28 diseases** and **25 quantitative traits**.
- Scores are estimated for individuals from various ethnic backgrounds with summary statistics from multi-ancestry and ancestry-specific GWAS studies.
- PRS data can be combined with data on socioeconomic risk factors to produce **Integrated Risk Scores (IRS)**.

List of Diseases and Quantitative Traits

No.	Diseases	Quantitative Traits
1	Alzheimer's disease	Age at menopause
2	Age-related macular degeneration (AMD)	Apolipoprotein A1
3	Asthma	Apolipoprotein B
4	Atrial fibrillation	Body mass index
5	Bipolar disorder	Calcium
6	Bowel cancer	Docosahexaenoic acid
7	Breast cancer	eGFR (creatinine)
8	Cardiovascular disease	eGFR (cystatin)
9	Coeliac disease	Estimated BMD T-score
10	Coronary artery disease	Glycated haemoglobin
11	Crohn's disease	HDL cholesterol
12	Hypertension	Height
13	Ischaemic stroke	Intraocular pressure
14	Melanoma	LDL cholesterol
15	Multiple sclerosis	Omega-3 fatty acids
16	Osteoporosis	Omega-6 fatty acids
17	Ovarian cancer	Phosphatidylcholines
18	Parkinson's disease	Phosphoglycerides
19	Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG)	Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs)
20	Prostate cancer	Remnant cholesterol
21	Psoriasis	Resting heart rate
22	Rheumatoid arthritis	Sphingomyelins
23	Schizophrenia	Total cholesterol
24	Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)	Total fatty acids
25	Type 1 diabetes	Total triglycerides
26	Type 2 diabetes	
27	Ulcerative colitis	
28	Venous thromboembolism (VTE)	

Pharmacogenetics / Pharmacogenomics (PGx)

- PGx is a study of how genetic differences influence response to various medications.
- PGx is a key tenet of **Accelerating Genomic Medicine** in the NHS plan but this requires large representative population research infrastructure such as that provided by Our Future Health.
- The Our Future Health custom genotype array is **enhanced for PGx**:
 - **Expert-led custom content** collation plus Illumina Enhanced PGx provide broad PGx coverage.
 - PGx star allele and variant coverage across **1700+ targets for over 50 genes**.
 - >6K annotated variants from PGx databases: **PharmGKB, CPIC, PharmVar, and ClinVar**, including hard-to-discern genes like CYP2D6, CYP2B6, and TPMT.
 - Robust CNV detection and targeted amplification to allow **PGx pseudogene disambiguation**.
- **Primary care** (upcoming) and **dispensed medication** datasets can be used to study PGx relationships.
- Research on participant genotypes that characterize the likelihood of **efficacy or adverse reactions, guide dosages, and identify novel indications** could improve clinical outcomes and prescribing cost effectiveness.

Molecular Blood Typing (MBT)

- The array contains ~18,200 variants enabling prediction of blood types:
 - **The 2 major blood groups** ABO and Rhesus
 - **8 minor blood groups**, e.g. Kell, Lutheran, Kidd, Duffy.
- Illumina is currently developing a **molecular blood typing algorithm** for use with the Our Future Health array. Plans for medical device certification.
 - Testing on the array demonstrated **96.7% concordance** with empirical data based on a set of 5,000 NHSBT participants.
 - Optimisation is expected to further improve the accuracy of blood typing.
- Data will be used by NHSBT as a pre-screen to identify **high-value donors** with rare blood types.

Our Future Health has designed and implemented an ultra-efficient, scalable recruitment model

Demographics of Our Future Health capture the diversity of the UK Population (2.5m consented)

Secure, de-identified data available to approved researchers right now

1,929,752	participants with baseline health questionnaires
1,841,458	participants with geographical data
775,118	participants with genotype array data
550,000	participants with genetic imputed data
1,690,845	participants with secondary care, cancer and death registration data
1,572,607	participants with dispensed medications
1,456,410	participants with clinic measurements data

+ Enhanced phenotyping of the Our Future Health cohort

Available Now	Next	Future
Baseline questionnaire	Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland data linkages	Additional data linkages (e.g., maternity, disease registries, census, GIS)
Custom genotype array data	Primary care linkage	Cognitive function (digital assessments and biomarkers)
Clinic appointment measures	Diabetes National Audit linkage	Wearable data (e.g., smartphone accelerometry, sleep)
Genotype imputation	Additional surveys (e.g., follow up, diet, cognitive function)	Additional omics (WGS, methylation, proteomics, metabolomics)
Dispensed medications		
Data linkage to NHS England secondary care, cancer registry, and deaths registry		

+ Our Future Health will catalyse discovery, aetiological and translational research

- The data currently available are providing **rich research insights for health**
 - Discover causal factors; unlock complex interactions; understand patient journeys; validate disease prediction/prognosis algorithms; evidence-based policy
- Our Future Health are **biobanking plasma, buffy coat and DNA**, and will facilitate access to stored biosamples for research studies
 - Many promising **diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers** fail at the stage of prospective evaluation. Our Future Health will solve this by being a **translational catalyst**
- Consent includes the **ability to recontact participants** to invite them to **receive health-related information** and to be selectively invited to **additional research studies and trials**
 - **Recruitment accelerator** for surveys, biospecimens, patient-centred research, interventions, and clinical trials which promise **benefits for participants and researchers**

Comment

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03438-0>

Our Future Health: a unique global resource for discovery and translational research

Michael B. Cook, Saskia C. Sanderson, John E. Deanfield, Fiona Reddington, Andrew Roddam, David J. Hunter & Raghieb Ali

 Check for updates

Our Future Health has recruited more than 1 million participants in the UK, with biobanked bloods, making it the largest consented cohort of its type in the world.

Our Future Health, a new prospective cohort study in the UK, has a mission to help people live longer, healthier lives through the discovery and testing of more-effective approaches to the prevention, earlier detection and treatment of diseases. Our Future Health is a charity supported by the UK government, industry and medical charities that aims to recruit 5 million volunteers from the UK adult population to create a unique resource that will catalyze etiological and translational research for both common diseases and rare diseases.

Healthcare systems across the world face an increasing burden of chronic diseases due to aging populations, with most conditions currently being detected only at an advanced stage, when they are much more difficult to treat effectively. In recognition of this, initial discussions exploring the need for a new very large cohort to address these public health challenges in the UK began in 2016 between several medical research charities, UK Research and Innovation, and leading public health practitioners and academics. The proposal to establish a 5-million-participant cohort that would combine health and other data to accelerate the development of preventative strategies, with earlier detection and diagnosis enabling earlier and more-effective treatments to be developed, was set out in the Accelerating Detection of Disease challenge of the government's Industrial Strategy Challenge Fund. In 2019, an investment of £79 million was allocated from this fund by UK Research and Innovation to establish Our Future Health, and over £180 million in conditional matched funding from industry and charity partners have been secured since then.

Our Future Health in the UK research landscape

Our Future Health builds on and complements the wider genetic and disease research infrastructure of the UK, in particular the major successes of UK Biobank¹, Genomics England, and the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Be Part of Research and BioResource. UK Biobank continues to facilitate a broad array of etiological

intervene, and how patients can be treated. The access to biological samples in this large prospective cohort will facilitate translational discoveries by enabling specific deep phenotyping of selected populations. Re-contact studies will enable the selection of participants on the basis of geography, demographics, genetics, phenotype and disease risk to be invited to consent to additional research studies and trials, catalyzing translational research.

The age, ethnic and geographic diversity of the cohort will facilitate extrapolation of findings to all communities, providing the largest multi-ethnic cohort, the largest cohort of young people (18–40 years of age), the largest working-age populations and the largest cohort of people over 60 years of age in the world. These features will provide subpopulations, mechanistic interactions and pre-diagnostic biospecimens to be studied in a level of detail not possible before. Our Future Health will be a learning system for the reframing of health care toward prevention that can ultimately feed into longitudinal personalized health programs² (<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/nhs-health-check-programme-review>). Planned serial enhancements in sequential surveys, expanded data linkages and ‘omics’ analyses will add additional depth in phenotyping, further expanding opportunities for research. An analytic environment amenable to machine learning- and artificial intelligence-based models will be facilitated to ensure maximal insights and discoveries.

Other programs in the UK research landscape that have less phenotypic and geographic breadth but are complementary to Our Future Health, serving somewhat different purposes, include the Scottish Health Research Register and Biobank, and Healthwise Wales. There are also other cohort studies, such as the European Prospective Investigation of Cancer and Nutrition³, Generation Scotland⁴, Genes & Health⁵, Growing Up in Wales⁶, the Million Women Study⁷, the Northern Ireland Cohort for the Longitudinal Study of Ageing⁸ and the Medical Research Council's new Adolescent Health Study⁹, among many others. This rich tapestry provides for a diversity of needs that no single program can provide.

Progress so far

Following the establishment of Our Future Health in 2019, an Ethics and Feedback Advisory Group developed the Ethics and Governance Framework. Over the next year, Our Future Health conducted extensive Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement work to ensure

<https://rdcu.be/d60Sr>

Cohort Profile: Our Future Health

Michael B. Cook^{1,2,3}, Naomi Adams¹, Ashley Adjetey¹, Ryan Arathimos¹, Marko Balabanovic¹, Ros Blackwood^{1,4}, Adam Booth¹, Benjamin J. Cairns¹, Ali Connell¹, Sidra Ellis¹, Ben Elsworth¹, Kate Evans¹, Alice Forman¹, Eva Gradovich¹, Cosima Gretton¹, Fiona Grimm¹, David J. Hunter^{3,5}, Kamil Lipinski¹, Jodie Lord¹, Jane Luff¹, Fiona Maleady-Crowe¹, Rachel Moran¹, Sophie North¹, Alicia Peel¹, Diana van der Plaats¹, Kirstin Purves¹, Fiona Reddington¹, Andrew Roddam⁶, Saskia C. Sanderson^{4,7,8}, Tim Sprosen¹, Adam Steventon¹, Iain Turnbull^{1,3}, Emma Vestesson¹, Raghbir Ali^{1,9,*}

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Keywords: cohort study; biobank; research volunteers selection; epidemiology; translational research; genetic research; pharmacoepidemiology; electronic health records; surveys and questionnaires; population health

Key Features

- Our Future Health is the UK's largest health research programme with an ambition to recruit 5 million UK-resident adult participants into a prospective cohort study.
- Our mission is to help everyone live longer, healthier lives through the discovery and testing of more effective approaches to the prevention, earlier detection, and treatment of diseases.
- Recruitment opened in October 2022. By June 2025, 2.4 million participants had consented, 1.8 million had completed the baseline questionnaire, 1.3 million had been linked to electronic health records, and 1.4 million had completed an in-person appointment to donate health metrics and blood.
- Genotyping is conducted using a 700 000-variant custom array that is optimized for multi-ethnic imputation and has up-to-date disease-, phenotype-, blood type-, and pharmacogenomic-associated variants.
- The cohort includes >600 000 people aged 18–40 years, facilitating research into diseases that disproportionately affect younger people, including obesity, mental health disorders, and addiction, and 900 000 people aged >60 years, enabling research into vascular dementia, Alzheimer's, and ageing.
- Our Future Health will catalyse translational research by facilitating access to stored biosamples and by enabling re-contact studies and trials with participants selectively invited based on demographics, phenotypes, and disease risks.
- To conduct research using the Our Future Health resource, please visit <https://research.ourfuturehealth.org.uk/>.

<https://academic.oup.com/ije/article/54/6/dyaf171/8287132>

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Access process

Our simple Access Process

- 1 Discover Our Future Health through our research resources
- 2 Create a researcher account
- 3 Apply to be a Registered Researcher
- 4 Request access to data for your study
- 5 Analyse the data in a secure environment
- 6 Generate findings and notify us of any changes

Researcher registration

- To become a Registered Researcher, your identity and credentials as a bonafide researcher are confirmed.
- Researchers submit a Researcher Application Form for review. Our Access Team review:
 - Identity of researcher
 - Affiliated organisation(s)
 - Technical skills to use the data safely
 - Complaints made against them in the last 3 years
 - Evidence of Information Governance (IG) training
 - Agreement of the Researcher Terms & Conditions

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Researcher application form

To access the Our Future Health data, you must become a registered researcher.

To apply, you will need to complete this application and submit evidence (for example a certificate) that you've completed information governance training within the past 12 months that covers UK GDPR

Once you submit your application, you'll get a response within 2 weeks.

1. About you

[Personal details](#)

Incomplete

[Countries you will access the data from](#)

Incomplete

[Professional profiles](#)

Incomplete

2. Affiliations

[Your current affiliations](#)

Incomplete

3. Employment and academic history

[Employment history](#)

Completed

[Academic history](#)

Incomplete

4. Publications and supporting information

[Relevant work](#)

Incomplete

[Supporting information](#)

Incomplete

5. Information governance training

[Training evidence](#)

Incomplete

6. Declarations

[Scientific and professional misconduct](#)

Incomplete

[Registered Researcher Terms and Conditions](#)

Incomplete

[Privacy policy](#)

Incomplete

[Application declaration](#)

Incomplete

Before you submit, review your application to make sure you've entered the correct information. Incorrect information can cause delays to your application.

[Review your application](#)

Study application

- A study application is required to allow Our Future Health approve access to the resource.
- Submit a Study Application Form to provide:
 - Proposed research, including a plain language summary.
 - Scientific details, including data requested and rationale.
 - List of all collaborators involved in the study.
 - Report funding and all declarations of interest associated with the study.
- Both individual researchers and their institutions need to agree to terms of use before they can access data.
- Decision on study applications within 60 days.

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Study application form

Study ID: OFHS1234567

To apply to access data, complete a study application form.

Complete the application using plain language. You can use our [Plain language guidance](#).

If you need to include scientific detail, explain it as clearly as possible. Do not use acronyms, jargon or complex language.

This is because some of the people in our Access Board are members of the public who do not have a scientific background.

It may delay your application if we need to check information with you.

1. Information that we will publish online

We will publish your name and the answers you give in this section on either the Our Future Health website or the Health Data Research Innovation Gateway website.

You can get readability scores for your answers with the [Hemmingway App](#). Aim for a score of Grade 6 or lower.

Your organisation	Incomplete
Plain language study title	Incomplete
Scientific study title	Incomplete
Study aim	Incomplete
Scientific rationale summary	Incomplete
How the study will benefit the public	Incomplete
Key words	Incomplete
Data required for your study	Incomplete
Funding	Incomplete
Data access	Incomplete
Study duration	Incomplete

2. Scientific detail and study design

Research study type	Incomplete
Accessing the data	Incomplete
Importing data	Incomplete
Scientific rationale	Incomplete
Study design and methods	Incomplete
Scientific quality review	Incomplete
Statistical review	Incomplete
Study limitations	Incomplete
Ethical issues	Incomplete
Involving the public	Incomplete
Related studies	Incomplete

+ Researcher resources

- Detailed documentation on resource data to support early discovery
- Researcher account to request and manage access
- TRE for secure data management and collaborative analysis at scale
- Technical and access-related support

The screenshot displays the Our Future Health researcher website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo, 'Researcher website', 'DNAnexus documentation', and a search bar. Below the navigation is a 'Programme design and recruitment' section with introductory text. A central hero section features the headline 'A world-leading resource for health research' and a call to action: 'Become a registered researcher at Our Future Health and apply for access to health data from the UK's largest health research programme.' Below this is a 'Contents' menu with links to 'Our growing data set', 'About the Our Future Health programme', and 'Our research resources'. The bottom portion of the image shows a 'Our growing data set' dashboard. This dashboard includes a 'Synthetic Data Cohort' with 5,151 participants and a 'pheno_v1_0_20230116.dataset' with 6,000 participants. It features several data preview panels: 'SR_GENDER_1_1' (5,151 Participants) showing a bar chart of gender distribution; 'SR_ETHNICITY_1_1' (5,151 Participants) showing a bar chart of ethnic groups; 'HOUSEHOLD_INCOME_1_1' (5,151 Questionnaires) showing a bar chart of income brackets; 'ACTIVITY_WALK_DAYS_1_1' (5,151 Questionnaires) showing a histogram of walking days; and 'WORK_WEEK_1_1' (5,151 Questionnaires) showing a box plot of work weeks. Each panel includes a search bar and a note about non-numeric values.

Our Future Health Trusted Research Environment

Enabled by
DNAnexus[®]

£500 cloud
credits to
get started

Easy data management

Powerful, intuitive cohort
browser

Combined clinical data and
omics information

Latest data releases available
quarterly

Accelerate analysis

Scalable analysis, with
JupyterLab & Spark

Genomics Apps, with Swiss
Army Knife & PLINK

CLI and multiple workflow
languages

Collaborative exploration

Share data, tools and analyses
efficiently with collaborators

Refined access, security, and
compliance made simple

Organisation tools to simplify
billing costs

Built around the Five Safes

How researchers access Our Future Health's secure data

1. Safe People

Researchers are trained and authorised to use data safely.

Registered Researcher

2. Safe Projects

Research studies are approved by Access Board for the public benefit.

Approved study

3. Safe Data

Data is treated to protect any confidentiality concerns.

Pseudonymised approved data

4. Safe Setting

A secure environment prevents unauthorised use.

5. Safe Output

Transfer between workspaces, with participant data, are screened via airlock to protect data.

Dissemination

Early research use cases

Full details will be published
on the HDRUK Gateway:

<https://healthdatagateway.org/en/data-custodian/86>

Title	Group
Investigating the risks of e-cigarettes in never smokers.	The University of East Anglia
Health and wellbeing among cancer survivors compared to those with no history of cancer: an analysis of Our Future Health data	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
Ethnicity and common cancers	University of Oxford
Identifying targets for new medicines using linked genetic and health data.	Alnylam
Genetic Research for Better Treatments for Patients	Roche
Cancer prevention in the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer/questioning, intersex, asexual, and other (LGBTQIA+) community	Queen Mary University of London
Large-Scale Analysis of Our Future Health Data to Facilitate Gene Discovery, Genome Sciences, and Genetic Medicines	Regeneron
Describing inequalities in health and use of healthcare in LGBTQ+ people	University College London

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Challenges and learnings

Planning ahead

The right time to automate

+ The 5 Vs of big data

Volume: very large amounts of data for a genetics-based context

Value: collecting data is one thing, but ensuring it has value to researchers is another

Velocity: the data is received continuously and processing must be timely and uninterrupted

Veracity: data can have a combination of issues

Variety: the data comes in a number of specialised file formats

+ The 5 Vs of big data

Define requirements
for the specific
combination of
challenges

Value: collecting data is one thing, but ensuring it has value to researchers is another

Volume: very large amounts of data for a genetics-based context

- Cloud based storage solution, autoscaling
- Efficient file types, next-generation formats
- Synthetic data to stress test processing times

Velocity: the data is received continuously and processing must be timely and uninterrupted

- CI/CD - data pipelines “always on” incremental daily QC to avoid backlogs
- Data schemas and file standardisation with hard rules for checks

Veracity: data can have a combination of issues

- Categorise issues; data integrity, statistical/biological
- Continuous monitoring, real-time feedback through dashboards
- Streamlined processes for troubleshooting non-conformances

Variety: the data comes in a number of specialised file formats

+ Three strikes and you automate

Automation is costly

- Development time
- Workflow complexity
- Reduced flexibility
- Maintenance
- Monitoring

First time - manually

Understanding the complexities, effort and dependencies
Produce: Code, system logs

Second time – manually (documented)

Understanding variability, automation strategy
Produce: Code, notes, internal documentation

Third time – automated

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Please [fill in the form](#)
to stay informed

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 [linkedin.com/in/ryanarathimos/](https://www.linkedin.com/in/ryanarathimos/)

Our Future Health data:
research.ourfuturehealth.org.uk/data-and-cohort/

For access related questions:
access@ourfuturehealth.org.uk

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